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Genes that mediate transition from CIN2 to carcinoma in the cervix.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We performed an expression screen to isolate genes important for progression of transformation *in vivo*, comparing total transcription in the CIN2 dysplastic stage and in frank carcinoma of the cervix. We describe induction of *Cxcl9* during progression to invasive malignancy *in vivo*.

Citations

1. Bill, R., Wirapati, P., Messemaker, M., Roh, W., Zitti, B., Duval, F., Kiss, M., Park, J.C., Saal, T.M., Hoelzl, J. and Tarussio, D., 2023. CXCL9: SPP1 macrophage polarity identifies a network of cellular programs that control human cancers. *Science*, 381(6657), pp.515-524.

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